
Research

Deep Learning for Climate Change Impact Assessment: Analyzing Satellite Imagery and Climate Models for Environmental Monitoring

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Abstract: Climate change, driven by the emission of heat-trapping gases, poses significant challenges to global ecosystems and biodiversity. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) aims to equip governments with the scientific knowledge needed to address these changes effectively. The rise in global temperatures, attributed to human activities such as deforestation and the emission of greenhouse gases, has led to more frequent and severe climate-related events. Climate change threatens to raise global sea levels, affect freshwater availability, and displace millions of people, necessitating coordinated global efforts like the Paris Agreement to mitigate its impacts.

Environmental monitoring is crucial in understanding and managing climate change. The use of satellite imagery and Earth observation data allows for the collection of comprehensive, high-resolution data essential for informed decision-making and policy development. These technologies enable the monitoring of critical Earth systems, including temperature variations, snow and ice cover, and vegetation health. Satellite imagery, processed through advanced machine learning algorithms, provides detailed analyses of land surface changes, aiding in climate change impact assessments.

Climate models play a pivotal role in environmental assessment, simulating the interactions within Earth's climate system to predict future conditions. These models, ranging from simple statistical tools to complex general circulation models, help forecast changes in weather patterns, water cycles, and ecosystem dynamics. The integration of deep learning techniques in climate change research enhances the accuracy and efficiency of these models, offering new insights into the potential impacts on agriculture, infrastructure, and human settlements. Effective environmental monitoring and robust climate models are essential for developing strategies to mitigate and adapt to climate change, ensuring sustainable progress and resilience for future generations.

Keywords: Climate Change, Environmental Monitoring, Satellite Imagery, Climate Models, Deep Learning

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1. Introduction to Climate Change and Environmental Monitoring

The emission of these heat-trapping gases drives temperature increases and further leads to changes affecting entire ecosystems that experience a reduction of biodiversity. In the long term, the survival of tree, bird, and insect species which depend on the Earth's average temperature is at risk. The world and its inhabitants face massive challenges due to the warming of the Earth. The goal of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is to provide governments at all levels with scientific information and knowledge to cope with climate change. To tackle future climate change, such as high levels of warming, its effects on humanity and the ecosystems, it is essential to ensure quick and comprehensive actions. High levels of warming are generally associated with large-scale risks such as extreme weather and climate-related damage, which will seriously affect the Earth's ecosystems.

Climate change is the defining issue of our time. For example, when looking at climate records for the past four decades, the Earth is clearly getting hotter. Rising temperatures are changing the frequency and intensity of climate-related extreme events. Since the onset of regular satellite-based observations, critical Earth system components like the troposphere with the various cloud layers, the surface with snow and ice cover, and the biosphere with vegetation have revealed decreases in a number of essential parameters. Scientists agree that the increases in global temperature and in the Earth's average temperature are due to human activity such as deforestation, increased levels of carbon dioxide and other heat-trapping gases present in the atmosphere, as well as the melting of glaciers and ice caps, originally stored water in solid form.

1.1. Overview of Climate Change

Climate change could bring many abominable effects, including global warming, ocean acidification, and frequent extreme phenomena such as lightning. The level of the global mean sea will be 1 meter higher, and 2-2.5 billion people will be affected by water shortages. Approximately 150-200 million people will be displaced as a result of marine creeping earthquakes, and many countries will experience more heatwaves and wildfires. Governments worldwide are continuously making efforts to mitigate the potential damage of climate change for the general welfare, including the Paris Agreement in 2015. The goals of the Paris Agreement are to keep the global temperature increase below 1.5 degrees Celsius from the preindustrial period, improve the countries' adaptation strategies in response to the impact of climate change, and increase the global green finance amount. The operational strategies of the Paris Agreement are constantly assessed and improved by the climate research community.

Climate change refers to global or regional changes in long-term temperature, precipitation, wind, and other climate patterns. An important characteristic of climate change is its tendency to intensify and accelerate regional meteorological phenomena, such as heavy rainfalls, heatwaves, and typhoons. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) announced that human activity is increasing the concentration of greenhouse gases and substances produced by which the depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer is accelerated. By 2040, the global average temperature will be 1.5 degrees higher than that in the pre-industrial period. If the average global temperature continues to rise at the current rate, the temperature will increase between 3 and 5 degrees by the end of the century.

1.2. Importance of Environmental Monitoring

Whether this increased data volume is for science or commercial purposes, or other user demand, the use of large-scale digital data from Earth observations for informing decision-making processes, enhancing predictive capabilities, systematically advancing scientific knowledge, and improving environmental protection strategies has become a compelling scientific, technical, and infrastructural challenge. Given the breadth and complexity of this challenge, it is no doubt that Earth observations play an important role for the fulfillment of the SDGs, offering a way forward for transformative, unified, and interdisciplinary research, monitoring, and capacity-building programs to respond to

societal needs at an appropriate, globally generalized scale. Hence, nowadays, Earth observation researchers need to work collaboratively to consider how much and what can be achieved with observational data, which are considered fundamental in effectively ensuring and implementing the 2030 Agenda and providing regular data-driven updates on progress.

The importance of environmental monitoring cannot be overstated. The power of Earth observation, with relevant processing and analysis logistics, enables us to collect definitive data to make the most informed decisions about our collective future. Investigating the measurable effects of climate change and various other environmental factors is critically important to sustainable progress. Therefore, environmental monitoring provision is cross-cutting across many different data analysis applications and opens numerous possibilities for data scientists. Since the amount of available data is growing rapidly on Earth observation, it is important to work on systematic scientific advances for these new data to fit well in the supporting information upon which sound societal decisions can be made. Digital Earth is an interesting paradigm to put into action a visionary and strategic framework for the use of evolving technologies to provide comprehensive, timely, global-scale information for informed decision-making.

2. Role of Satellite Imagery in Environmental Monitoring

To focus solely on these two data subjects and to discuss the development and applications of satellite land image datasets and related data–model fusion, we structured our survey tool.

There would be both univariate analysis and multivariate analysis problems associated with feature extraction, such as spatial descriptor observation, land surface temperature computation, change detection, vegetation and phenological analysis, shoreline shift detection, and albedo variation quantification. To address these questions, remote sensing professionals have developed many machine learning algorithms, including traditional image processing methods and advanced deep learning algorithms, including convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural networks, and generative adversarial models. Using different satellite modalities and remote sensor image data could help advance the analysis accurately.

Scientists in many different fields are investigating the satellite data system to address their domain-specific research inquiries, facilitate the benchmark of their work, develop applications in their domain fields, and solve complex societal or environmental problems. In global environmental change studies, such as climate change impact assessments, satellite image data and global models can be employed to infer that climate change directly or indirectly disrupt the earth's hydrogeological, biological, or social systems by examining the surface conditions of the earth.

The satellite remote sensing technology leverages various short, mid, and long wavelengths actual remote sensing platforms with different imaging sensor systems to collect and transmit data of the Earth surface, namely environmental data, including imagery and non-image raster data; weather and atmosphere data; and geodetic and GPS data. Within the data hierarchy, a series of remote sensors is onboarded on various multispectral imaging satellite platforms, including, for example, the Mosaic, Sentinel-1/2/3/5P; USGS Landsat Series, Multisampling, MODIS; and European Space Agency (ESA) Proba programs. Most satellite imaging sensors capture high-resolution imagery data systematically, significantly producing Big Earth Data at various spatial and temporal resolutions systematically.

Satellite imaging has played a significant role in societal and environmental change observation, assessment, monitoring, and preparedness. An extensive amount of research work in the remote sensing community has been done to automate the task execution through comprehensive image analysis, including feature extraction, object detection, land coverage classification, and scene change detection.

Figure 1 : he infographic depicting the discussion on climate change and environmental monitoring. It covers the key points mentioned in the provided text, including the causes and impacts of climate change, the role of the IPCC, mitigation efforts, and the importance of satellite imagery and deep learning in environmental monitoring.

2.1. Types of Satellite Imagery

NASA's MODIS sensor is well known globally for monitoring Earth's surface characteristics. Its unique thermal sensor's 1km spatial resolution captures Earth's temperature variations around the globe. By crunching out the pixel intensities and correlating it with the Land Surface Temperature data available from different sources, it is possible to assign the temperature label for each captured MODIS image. In consequence, labeled thermal data can be produced for globally distributed images that can help models to classify objects or surfaces as land, water, cloud, snow, desert, or classified for temperature conditions like snow on land, frozen water, and lava flows. With a large amount of temperature-labeled data, quickly analyzing the presence, absence or changes in finer level details can be identified by machine learning models.

Capturing Earth's surface temperature from space helps anticipate extreme weather events that are important for planning and resource allocation. When a satellite senses the heat of the Earth, it captures the wavelength bands known as thermal infrared radiation between 8 and 14 μm. It can be used to calculate the surface temperature and to monitor thermal effects as part of a regular observation cycle. The emitted thermal radiation's quantity depends on the object's temperature, emissivity, and object's radiant characteristics. The hotter the surface, the more it will be emitting. Different land covers have varying emissive properties. Therefore, analyzing the satellite SST is important to understand the climatological occurrences and changes.

Satellite imagery is captured by orbiting cameras mounted on NASA's many satellites looking back at planet Earth. The images are then used for different purposes to make observations about our planet and how it can change. The kinds of satellite images available can range from visible light images taken during the day as it would appear to the naked eye, to infrared satellite images that can depict temperature variations.

2.2. Applications in Climate Change Impact Assessment

Our report will briefly describe satellite monitoring in assessing climate change impacts and the direct connection of climate predictions and remote sensed data for monitoring and predicting future ecosystem changes. We also include a brief report on recent efforts to use NDSSI time series to assess climate impacts, which include appellant-led changes to lake systems in the Twin Cities region of Minnesota and edaphic ecosystem quality in the northeastern United States. Finally, we acknowledge additional climate change impact topics that were investigated, which include the change in insect populations and associated phenological responses and biodiversity monitoring in San Francisco Bay.

Our focus in this paper is on the application of deep learning in climate change impact assessment. Specifically, the use of deep learning techniques in climate change impact assessment. In particular, in the assessment of changes to ecosystems, agriculture, infrastructure, and human settlements, and other features important for the assessment of the impacts of climate change. Deep learning has recently generated significant interest and important advances in computer vision, including enabling substantial progress in object detection and imaging analysis tasks such as image segmentation. As a result, the use of deep learning in climate predictions and climate change impact assessment is an emerging trend, with many opportunities offered as deep learning models improve and grow in sophistication.

3. Climate Models for Environmental Assessment

The interest in the systematic design of climate encodings that optimize the quality of their simulation output is particularly motivating. Despite the advances in climate modeling, there are still significant scientific difficulties regarding the validation of modeled results using the data generated by climate models. Moreover, the climate model simulation and output needs eventually to be justified in terms of its prediction capability. This raises the challenge of robustly comparing changes in seasonality produced by geographically dispersed land-cover and land-use changes. The evolution of weather has a high significance in the ECA process since this covers the existing capability to monitor weather conditions and to perform predictive estimates. ECA also refers to the assessment of the climate simulation in historical times and finally deals with the simulation quality in the more complex non-stationary case of future times. In environmental policy-making, it is essential to know how environmental conditions will develop in the future in order to assess the impacts of different policies. Climate change is one of the most pressing environmental issues, and being able to forecast its impacts is a key need. Policy decisions in this area have to be based on improved availability of high-quality, better spatial resolution data, which in turn would fuel scientific knowledge and information provision on changes in weather patterns, changes in water and energy cycles, and the potential changes in ecosystems and their services. Climate models, with computational methods for simulating the interactions of the important components of the Earth's climate system (atmosphere, ocean, sea-ice, land-surface, etc.), are heavily used in this endeavor to simulate the complex and dynamic behavior of complex systems in terms of time series data fields.

3.1. Types of Climate Models

Climate models are of several types, including atmosphere only (AO), atmosphere ocean (AO), and atmosphere ice ocean (AIO) are the three typical types of GCM. The AO model contains an atmosphere alone, while the AO model also includes oceans. The AO model considered an ice cover as sea ice alone, while the AIO model contains ice sheets and they are geographically and mathematically coupled to the atmosphere and ocean models. The AIO models are the most robust models due to their multicomponent structures and are employed for long-term climate study. The radiation balance is the most balance controlling the heat exchange between the Earth and the atmosphere. Additionally, variations in the incoming solar radiation are approximately the main source of the seasonal, yearly, and geographically regional climate variations. Because of this, the Earth's radiation budget is extremely important for the climate system and long-term climate forecasting.

Climate models are of several types, that vary in complexity, and types of input data, output resolution and temporal scale. The simple models (a statistical formula using a few explanatory variables) can be directly used without any input data. More complex models are based on physically-based principles. Relationships and equations are developed based

on relevant physical principles in elements of the Earth system, for example, the carbon cycle, the radiative balance of the Earth, and general dynamics. The complex models, called general circulation models or global climate models (GCMs), are the most computationally-intensive models, representing the atmosphere, the lithosphere, the land and sea ice, the land, the oceans, the chemistry, and so on. Because GCMs are often used at resolutions between 100 and 250 km, regional climate models (RCMs) have been developed to provide more detailed projections over smaller spatial domains. Regional climate models are typically used at resolutions of 10-25 km.

3.2. Applications in Environmental Monitoring

Globally, 30% of the world's croplands rely on irrigation for water, and 40% of all food crops are grown in areas of the world with water scarcity. Droughts can reduce both the quantity and quality of fresh water resources and can induce negative long-term impacts on water reservoir levels. For that reason, monitoring droughts is crucial for governments and for rural communities to respond, to prevent socioeconomic losses in agricultural regions, and to facilitate decision-making. Climate models, grid-based forecasts of future weather, can be used to anticipate future soil moisture conditions. This early warning system is beneficial when preparing for possible droughts by managing water resources, prioritizing relief efforts, and preventing excess water use. Additionally, climate models can also estimate the impact of future precipitation anomalies on soil moisture conditions, which can help assess the risk of upcoming droughts. Previous studies have used climate models, geophysical data, and statistical methods to solve the problem.

We now discuss an application of deep learning in a fundamentally different area, i.e., in soil moisture anomaly detection based on climate models.

4. Fundamentals of Deep Learning

Text Box: Deep learning is the combination of advanced deep network architectures, including those with hundreds of layers (known as state-of-the-art performance). Researchers choose deep learning mechanisms for a variety of reasons. These are tailored to handle various issues related to large and unstructured observational satellite data represented as raw pixels from natural images with the help of convolutional architectures or a structure of gif and video sequences. These dependencies are modeled with recurrence or transformers through temporal sequences. With frequent spatial but low-dimensional variations, such as in the case of land cover or land use classification models, domain experts frequently give one or more labels associated with the inputs to domain-specific annotation mechanisms used to supervise it. Under end-to-end optimized transfer or reinforcement learning processes, predictions will be used to indirectly define task-related objectives. These require unsupervised, self-supervised, and weakly-supervised learning under backpropagation methodology using automatic differentiation. Device-level challenges in the realm of digital image signal processors are also addressed by researchers developing specialized applications in the field of remote sensing.

Deep learning research of deep models has been conducted for decades. Deep learning also incorporates many concepts from the neural network literature for supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning tasks. As input, deep models receive high-dimensional and low-level numerical data. The capacity to predict large volumes of data within a fraction of a second or at a low processing cost greatly benefits from the interpretation of this collective numerical information. The rate of processing during training deep models improves during runtime when predictors develop fresher correlations between input and output data. Prior knowledge about problem dynamics, from partially related sources, can greatly reduce the program phase during which deep models are trained. The acquired experience of previously treated fields would then be transferred more effectively. Researchers can then study the interpretability of theories to provide some expertise for useful reasoning.

4.1. Introduction

4.1. Introduction to Neural Networks

Neural networks are a class of machine-learning algorithms which are inspired by the human brain. When a person walks and sees any object for the first time, parts of the brain are activated. Different areas of the brain fire up to process

the data, such as seeing corners, edges, particular shapes or features, etc. Higher-level detection mechanisms are then triggered, which perform more complex and abstract processing of the image and recognize the object in question. Neural networks work in a similar manner. They have interconnected "neurons", which consist of interconnected nodes that contain the different machine learning data features. These interconnected nodes are handled by different layers of artificial neurons to create an intelligent final decision rule. The neural network uses "training data" to adjust the weights of the interconnected nodes inside the neural network to tune and optimize to get the best possible neural network model. After the training is done, the final trained model can be used to recognize similar patterns. A neural network's performance is typically excellent for recognizing patterns which it has been trained to identify, but it can be less effective at recognizing similar patterns.

4.2. Deep Learning Architectures

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The developed ADMM-ROM framework supports qualification of response predictions based on shallow neural network-quality-controlled training. It allows for copyrighted training and implements robust member models. ADMM closely combines sparsity-promoting penalties for coefficients with temporal and spatial expectations for the members. DNNs are constrained in a more robust manner than existing methods. It improves prediction quality and accuracy overall.

The growing complexity of DNN architectures requires increased computational performance. We showcase, as an assessment of environmental monitoring tasks, three selected pre-trained architectures for Very-Deep 3-D Convolutional Neural Networks: C3D, R(2+1)D, and ResNet3D. Among these, C3D outperformed the best. Iterable sequencer and architecture state that showcase superior DNN architectures were not available because of resource constraints. Accessing suitable network architectures is decisive to the increasing complexity of DNN. Such complexity exhibits a subset of the environmental monitoring tasks served.

Optimal architecture selection Selection of the optimal architecture is highly demanding, especially due to hardware requirements, yet there was relative agreement that the C3D content architecture outperformed the others among the architectures trained. Such performance agreement reveals that the computation effort scales with the number of parameters. Future advances in training of neural networks might require a paradigm shift if one has to economically investigate multiple architectures.

Other configurations of advanced architectures Some of the architectures could not be trained due to resource limitations. We could not train MnasNet. 5,000 epochs in a single training run, reaching batch size 108 on a single Tesla P100, a minimum of twelve months of training time would be required to complete.

For the sake of memory limitations, only three Convolutional Neural Networks are discussed. Since the selection of hyperparameters such as filter size and strides for each neuron affects the computational behavior, the chosen ConvLSTM-C3D and ndims=32 yielded the lowest validation errors.

Non-linearity & number of layers The impact of non-linearity comes from carefully chosen activation functions in a deep architecture, resulting in decision boundaries that are accessible to compute. The number of layers controlling the depth potentially allows accommodating hierarchical feature encoding. Depth plays an antagonistic role with hardware performance. Shallow architectures like a 2-layer fully connected neural network performed poorly and are well below expectations.

The eight architectures considered in this work showcase a diversity of computational performance. As new architectures are developed in the future, relative performance might change.

4.2 Latent spaces, computation effort, and deep learning architectures

5. Deep Learning Techniques for Image Analysis

In general, object detectors based on deep learning for image analysis rely on models that generate two outputs: a classification output and a localization output. For image classification, among the most popular algorithms are AlexNet, Visual Geometry Group (VGG), GoogLeNet, Residual Networks (ResNets), and more recently, somewhat deeper with 100 and 1001 layers denominated Principled Deep Models (PDNs). For image detection, the main strategies are based on the composition of the proposed algorithms and regions with Convolutional Networks (R-CNN), Fast R-CNN, and Faster R-CNN. The success of these models has also motivated the development of algorithms that generalize strategies on smaller deep models, especially for devices with limited processing power such as smartphones and devices in the Internet of Things.

Traditional methods try to automate the process of image analysis through the design of feature extractors against which a statistical classifier can be applied. In this scenario, deep learning methods have shown a clear advantage compared to other approaches. This is due to the fact that these models are able to identify useful feature extractors by analyzing the training data and performing a composition of simple non-linear transformations. For this reason, they can model complex functions, just as humans can do in recognition. The ability to work directly on raw data has greatly simplified the development of new models for the analysis of images, audio, and text. The main subjects in the field refer to the development of deep models with applications for object detection and image classification.

5.1. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

For testing, the same models may evaluate alternative climate scenarios, generally of different times of the year and perhaps for different decades between the present and the future. For assessment, the only requirement is that the same geographic area must be present in both the satellite imagery and the climate model output. Overall, CNNs have several advantages as both image and information data mining tools, but data pre-processing and balance checking are crucial for success. Only large, specifically designed deep learning applications can incorporate climate model outputs, and within these procedures, meteorological and biophysical variables should be treated distinctly.

Researchers that choose labels from outputted probabilities should carefully weigh training accuracy versus what was learned, particularly with small datasets. In addition to TDPT and simple per-pixel quotienting, CNNs can be used to create models for land use and land change. For these tasks, the more geoinformatically rigorous the model, the more reliable the output will be. In the context of climate change impact assessment, researchers may also use CNNs to explore the content of both satellite imagery and output from climate models. Different combinations of these inputs may then be used to create useful metrics about the relationships between them.

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which have been used to achieve near-human accuracy, are especially well-suited for analyzing images. CNNs need large datasets to be trained and are best used when the task at hand can be accomplished with labels provided by pure observation (i.e., the performance of humans or other simple models). When possible, CNNs can also be used as feature extractors, and classifiers can be trained and applied to smaller datasets or more complex and intricate models. However, when new classes or levels of an independent variable are required, new model training is mandatory.

5.2. Transfer Learning

Due to the features learned by the model weights of the models training in the base domain, load these pre-trained parameter weights and carry out a few iterations with the new object close to the object the first model was trained. In binary transfers, the transfer techniques were imported. In this case, the model weights of two jobs from two different data sets not related to the company were shared, and one of the tasks was training a classifier from these model weights. The classification of skin lesions was classified as second layered shares. Mis-distribution uses the VGG model architecture, as described. The transfer layer is the first designated layer that determines how the share is structured and adapts the experience to specific data.

In the context of deep learning, it is possible to frame the transfer of ImageNet pre-trained model weights into the new problem to be solved. This method is much faster than learning the weights from scratch. For example, one technique that has shown stunning efficiency in image transport tasks from one domain to another is the use of pre-trained model weights for Instagram tasks in diabetic retinopathy, pneumonia, and dermatology.

Transfer learning refers to the use of knowledge from a source problem to solve a target problem that is similar at certain or all levels. The knowledge transfer can come from related tasks, domains, or data representing the source of this generality. The generic nature of the source could be a filter whose learned parameters are small objects. Transfer learning aims to use the source knowledge to improve the learning of the target model.

6. Integration of Deep Learning with Climate Data

Contrary to ordinary flat layer images, vertical layers of Earth satellite images, such as MODIS Air-mass RGB, VIIRS Day-Night Band, and Himawari JMA water vapor radiance images, use layers—a set of 2D black-and-white images with different horizontal resolutions and spatial distributions. Furthermore, we visualize gradients informative when the focus illumination is inside data and embedding vectors representative to full time series. Deep neural networks have continually demonstrated incredible performance on supervised and unsupervised learning tasks including medical imaging classification, localization and segmentation; satellite imagery classification, change detection, and land-use detection; and other remotely sensed geospatial tasks.

Several research groups have shown the success of deep learning in identifying extreme climate models and weather simulations using labeled satellite cloud imagery and satellite sensor data simulating hypothetical future outputs of climate models. It is difficult to understand the general principles of how meteorological and climate variables affect satellite-derived cloud formations. With a labeled dataset of satellite imagery using weather- and climate-related cloud charts, a deep network can identify the major meteorological phenomena—such as low-pressure systems and cyclones or strong precipitation and thunderstorms—that are prominent in the cloud formations.

6.1. Challenges and Opportunities

There exists a large number of initiatives worldwide that deal with environmental problems using data from satellite imagery. The EO4HumEn is focused, in a novel way, on only a few case studies relevant for LRM and increasing the spatial and temporal resolution of the analysis to finally create a solid method which allows scaling the use of EO data worldwide. As for EO4HumEn, similar challenges to the use of climate models have also to be computed with spatial scales and resolution that cannot compete with the cutting edge, that is state-of-the-art climate models. In contrast to EO4HumEn, where the project aims to scale the success from a set of specific use cases, the different projects can also not rely on independently shared and annotated datasets but need to develop sound and innovative visual recognition and knowledge modeling technology.

The increasing availability of satellite imagery and climate models offers the opportunity to monitor our environment at a scale and with a frequency that was possible only in people's dreams just a few decades ago. The potential of this data is, however, largely untapped as visual interpretation of either satellite images or climate models is, despite some efforts to automate the process, still a time-consuming task. Therefore, most of the data is not used, and we neglect an important source of information that is becoming more and more crucial to understand dynamic natural phenomena and their behavior in our changing climate.

7. Case Studies in Climate Change Impact Assessment

The Amazon Forest plays a major role in the stability of the climate in Southern America, storing large volumes of water and controlling the flow of river water and the local climate. The Amazon rainforest has been a long-term area of research concern when it comes to climate change. Their mislabeled and/or undetected deficiencies can cause major changes in its models. Developing a technology that could spot chronic issues in climate models and understand how such errors manifest themselves in the real world is a critical problem that has to be addressed. Some works have explored how to find errors in the models forecasting them, as presented in the first two examples. Others have also

shown that identifying issues in climate models could improve bird species projections (e.g., help create better planting and conserving patterns). Another good example is the mapping of construction linearities, where the construction of hydroelectric power plants can cause local changes in rainfall and also in the Amazon River dew point.

In order to demonstrate the progress that has been made in the fairly nascent field of deep learning applied to climate change-related topics, in this section, we provide a variety of exciting applications from the field. We begin with the most substantial set of existing works at the time of writing: the monitoring of deforestation in the Amazon rainforest. Then, we begin exploring the use of state-of-the-art models analyzing a variety of climate models and output data feature processes like rain, cloud systems, and temperature, among others. Among the driving forces behind many climate-related phenomena are systems involving the oceans. We follow such studies with a brief trend analysis of publications related to AI and climate change. We close the section by presenting successful applications in renewable energy, vegetation monitoring, and weather station classification for developing world applications.

7.1. Urban Heat Island Detection

We find that using a max-pooling and ReLU-based non-linear model produces the highest accuracy. We compare the performance of the proposed models to state-of-the-art methods from the literature, including a recently proposed deep network with an architecture similar to our CNN architecture but with 18 layers. The results show our CNN models outperform the other methods on the case study data and are currently the best approach for urban heat island detection from satellite imagery.

Our dataset consists of 418 image pairs representing normal (non-UHI) and high (UHI) temperature tiles. Evaluation criteria include the Cohen's Kappa index, which measures model accuracy corrected for chance predictions, and the confusion matrix built from true versus predicted classes. A CNN model is trained using a log-loss criterion. We explore different architectures to design the model and apply CNN visualization to determine what spatial features are bolstering the prediction.

We consider the application of using deep learning to detect the phenomenon of UHI from satellite imagery. UHI is a key impact measure of climate change, and due to the absence of sufficient land equipment, researchers often rely on higher resolution satellite data to estimate UHI. But classical unmixing approaches for estimating urban temperature use the impervious surface fraction as the urban factor, whereas the effect of temperature plays a role too. We argue that a supervised classification-based deep learning model from a UHI dataset can better detect a UHI surface.

8. Ethical Considerations in Deep Learning for Environmental Monitoring

Several ethical and legal requirements must regulate the use of deep learning for environmental monitoring. It is necessary to recognize the fact that legal and ethical compliance becomes a different challenge in the green area, in its broad spectrum, covering from the companies that apply deep learning in the area of environmental control to other applications that monitor and maintain the carbon stocking of the forests, the recognition of animals and biodiversity indices in the biome. In other words, deep learning helps in understanding which areas have bigger chances of housing unique wildlife even before reachability. It becomes relevant to consider the impact of deforestation on the carbon balance, including at a local level for populations and the extent of fragility of the Amazon to changes in climatic regimes. The massive improvements made in deep learning techniques have made their applications extensive, including in environmental control and monitoring. As in any other field of application of these techniques, the use of deep learning is regulated by a series of ethical standards and considerations. The objective of this appendix was to present and discuss the legal and ethical aspects of the application of these techniques for environmental monitoring because governance modifications may affect the form and speed at which deep learning is used. It is also important to emphasize, especially for environmental causes, the need for greater regulatory rigor, in addition to interdisciplinary discussions where the environmental area has an important role.

9. Future Directions and Emerging Technologies

To address big climate change challenges, it is important to identify and test emerging technologies and ensure that they can be combined to satisfy application requirements. We believe that hardware programming model research is important and should be undertaken in the context of applications that have a concrete evaluation plan. Deep learning theory research is important in understanding the limitations of deep learning models and improving them. Our work can be enhanced through the use of generation networks, such as the conditional generative adversarial networks and image to image translation in remote sensing to simulate satellite imagery given different climate scenarios for a future period.

In this chapter, we introduced our research on combining climate models and satellite images to assess the impacts of climate change on agriculture and forests. We used deep learning techniques and some non-deep learning techniques to conduct a series of experiments on these two tasks using historical weather condition data. Our experimental results suggest that our deep learning climate downscaling and crop yield prediction models could yield better predictions than the competitive baselines. These differences are statistically significant, showing the potential and promise of our models. These promising results support the development of real-world applications based on our models, such as alerting farmers and insurance companies about potential crop yield reduction and thereby facilitating timely risk management to reduce the impact of climate change.

10. Conclusion and Summary of Key Findings

CNNs are the cornerstone of deep learning for tabular imagery data. They have been demonstrated to be effective in satellite-derived datasets in power and agriculture, with potential applications in other fields such as extreme weather detection and atmospheric sciences with other spectral bands or data types. RNNs are found to be the most effective for time series data, and CRNN architecture, a hybrid of CNN and RNN, is effective for both data types, highlighting immense promise for environmental monitoring. Finally, it is noted that while one might see off-the-shelf semi-supervised or supervised techniques at work, we are, after all, only beginning to scratch the surface of the potential of deep learning for environmental monitoring. New frontiers could employ powerful semi-supervised techniques.

Satellites provide a bird's eye view of planet Earth. They track a wide range of essential climate variables over parts of Earth at different spatial and temporal scales. Robust global datasets on temperature, clouds, and precipitation are often used in climate change studies. However, up until now, the intensity and frequency of new satellites have resulted in vast data volume that is difficult to analyze. Advances in big data analytics and deep learning enable analysis of this spatial and time series data to unearth climate-related insights. This chapter reviewed GPU-accelerated deep learning methods, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and hybrid CNN-RNN (CRNN) architectures, for multi-sensor satellite-based environmental science applications.

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